

Preparation of 1-formyl-8-hydroxy carbazole(VI) :

The crude product obtained in the previous step was dissolved in dry xylene (50 ml). To this solution a solution of DDQ (5 g) in dry xylene (20 ml) was added gradually. A green precipitate of the hydroquinone immediately appeared. After the addition, the whole content was refluxed for 20 hours and then filtered to separate the hydroquinone formed. The filtrate was concentrated and then chromatographed over silica gel when petroleum ether-benzene mixture (3 : 1) eluent on concentration and crystallisation from petroleum ether gave pure yellow crystals of 1-formyl-8-hydroxy carbazole(VI), m. p. 120°, $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3400-3440, 1685, 1600, 1590, 1500, 760, 730 cm^{-1} and $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 311 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 2.2), 289 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 2.65), 280 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 2.55), 251 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 2.37) and 220 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.4). Yield 50%.

The p.m.r. spectrum (90 MHz) of the compound in CDCl_3 showed the presence of $-\text{NH}-$ proton (δ 10.27, s, 1H) and $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{CHO}$ protons (δ 10.00, broad singlet, 2H, one proton disappeared on D_2O exchange) and aromatic protons at C_8 and C_6 (δ 7.52, quartet, 2H) and aromatic proton at C_2 (δ 8.3, d, $J=8\text{Hz}$, 1H) and other three aromatic protons at C_4 , C_5 and C_7 (δ 8.15, d, $J=7.5\text{Hz}$, 1H; δ 7.85, d, $J=7.5\text{Hz}$, 1H and δ 7.3, d, $J=7\text{Hz}$, 1H).

Analytical data :

Found : C, 73.7% ; H, 4.3%, N, 6.65% Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N}$: C, 73.92% ; H, 4.29% ; N, 6.63%.

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Synthesis of Coumarins (2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyrans) and Benzocoumarins (2-Oxo-2H-1-naphthopyrans)

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SYNTHESIS of coumarins, thiocoumarins and carbostyrils have been reported^{1,2} from cinnamoyl derivatives of phenols, thiophenols and anilines with anhydrous aluminium chloride. Phenyl cinnamates furnish either coumarins or dihydrocoumarins depending on the solvents employed. With tetrachloroethane, only dihydrocoumarins^{3,4} have been isolated, whereas, employing chlorobenzene as a solvent gave coumarins¹.

We intend to report in the present paper, the synthesis of coumarins following an analogous pathway as earlier reported^{1,2}. The corresponding intermediates-phenyl and naphthyl furylacrylates required in the synthesis, were obtained in high yields by reacting phenols and naphthols with furylacrylic acid in the presence of phosphoryl chloride and a base. These esters were then cyclised with anhydrous aluminium chloride in chlorobenzene to furnish the desired coumarins and benzocoumarins.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected.

Phenyl furylacrylates : The corresponding phenol (0.065 mole) and furylacrylic acid (0.07 mole) was dissolved in 70-80 ml pyridine. Solution was cooled to 10° and POCl_3 (4 ml) added dropwise with stirring. After the addition of POCl_3 , the mixture was stirred for 2 hrs at room temperature and then poured into cold, dil. HCl. The precipitated product was filtered, washed with water and triturated with 2N NaHCO_3 , filtered and washed with water. The product was then crystallized from ethanol to give yields varying between 90-95% (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHENYL FURYLACRYLATES

R	m.p. (°C)	Mol. Formula	Analysis(%)			
			Calc.		Found	
			C	H	C	H
H	42-3	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ O ₃	72.90	4.67	72.89	4.58
CH ₃	52	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃	73.69	5.26	73.62	5.19
NO ₂	158	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ N	60.23	3.47	60.14	3.88

Naphthyl furylacrylates : 1- and 2-Naphthyl furylacrylates were obtained by condensing 1- and 2-naphthols with furylacrylic acid by the method given above.

1-Naphthyl furylacrylate, m.p. 45°; yield 92%. (Found : C, 77.21; H, 4.44; C₁₇H₁₂O₃ requires C, 77.27; H, 4.55%), 2-Naphthyl furylacrylate, m.p. 70°; yield 95%. (Found : C, 77.18; H, 4.49; C₁₇H₁₂O₃ requires C, 77.27; H, 4.55%).

Coumarin (2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran) and 6-substituted derivatives (Table 2) :

The respective furylacrylates prepared as above (3 g) were dissolved in dry chlorobenzene (30 ml) and mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (9 g). The mixture was heated under reflux on a water-bath for 1.5 to 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was decomposed by the addition of ice and dil. HCl and extracted with CHCl₃. The chloroform extract was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated to yield the product which was purified by crystallisation in ethanol or chromatographed over a silica gel column, employing hexane, benzene, chloroform and methanol, in the order, as eluants in varying proportions.

Benzocoumarins (2-oxo-2H-1-naphthopyrans) :

1- and 2-Naphthyl furylacrylates when subjected to the above method gave respectively 7, 8-benzocoumarin, m.p. 140-1°; yield 52% (Found : C, 79.46; H, 3.92, C₁₃H₈O₂ requires C, 79.57; H, 3.99%), IR (ν_{max}^{KBr} in cm⁻¹) : 1724; UV (in 95% EtOH), λ_{max} 219 nm, and λ_{min} 308 nm.

5,6-Benzocoumarin, m.p. 118°; yield 46% (C₁₃H₈O₂; Found : C, 79.51; H, 3.95%), IR (KBr) : 1720 cm⁻¹ UV (in 95% EtOH) λ_{max} 231 nm, and λ_{min} 317 nm.

[IR (KBr) : 1700, 1720 and 1735 cm⁻¹ for R=H, -CH₃ and -NO₂ respectively (>C=O) ;

UV_{max}^{MeOH} ; 312 nm (R=H), 310 nm (R=CH₃), and 314 nm (R=NO₂)]

TABLE 2—6-SUBSTITUTED COUMARINS

R	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Mol. Formula	Analysis(%)			
				Calc.		Found	
				C	H	C	H
H	70	73	C ₉ H ₆ O ₂	73.96	4.11	73.89	4.02
CH ₃	74-5	65	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂	75.01	5.0	74.87	4.92
NO ₂	185-6	78	C ₉ H ₅ O ₄ N	56.54	2.62	56.42	2.52

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Malhotra and Katoch's "Solvates" of Alkali Acetates with Acetic Anhydride— A Reinvestigation

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WE were fascinated by the report of Malhotra and Katoch¹ on the successful synthesis of MOAc-Ac₂O complexes where M is an alkali cation and Ac₂O denotes acetic anhydride. To clear our own doubts we repeated the work and found that the MOAc products (M=Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺ and NH₄⁺) were in fact M(OAc, HOAc) acid salts; the products obtained by these workers¹ by the reaction of MOAc with Ac₂O were the same as we obtained